

Preliminary Physical Design of Thorium-based High Temperature Gas-cooled Reactor Based on the HTR-PM

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803765

ABSTRACT

Thorium, as a potentially utilizable nuclear fuel, has not yet been widely adopted in the nuclear energy industry. The key to harnessing thorium-based fuels lies in achieving the conversion of Th-232 to U-233. High Temperature Gas-cooled Reactors (HTGRs) exhibit excellent neutron economy and possess a higher proportion of thermal neutrons in the spectrum compared to pressurized water reactors, which is more conducive to the breeding of U-233. Moreover, pebble-bed HTGRs employ online continuous refueling, allowing for more flexible fuel management strategies. Based on the HTR-PM design, this study conducts a physical design analysis of thorium-based fuel cycles. The results indicate that discharge burnup, moderation ratio, and core size are critical factors affecting the conversion ratio. These parameters significantly influence the breeding potential of thorium-based fuels by modulating neutron leakage and parasitic neutron absorption.

Keywords: high temperature gas-cooled reactor (HTGR), thorium-based fuel cycle, conversion ratio

1. INTRODUCTION

Thorium, as a potentially utilizable nuclear fuel, possesses reserves approximately 3 to 4 times greater than those of uranium [1]. However, it has not yet been widely adopted within the nuclear energy industry. Natural thorium contains 99.98% Th-232, enabling its direct use in nuclear fuel fabrication without requiring isotopic separation. Utilizing thorium resources for nuclear fuel production is expected to reduce fuel costs.

While Th-232 is a fertile nuclide that undergoes minimal fission with neutrons, it can be converted into a fissile nuclide through a series of nuclear reactions. Figure 1 shows the nuclear reaction chain of the thorium-uranium fuel cycle. Specifically, Th-232 absorbs a neutron to form Th-233, which then undergoes beta decay to form Pa-233. Subsequently, Pa-233 decays via beta emission to form U-233. U-233 readily undergoes fission with thermal neutrons to release energy. The effective utilization of thorium resources could significantly alleviate the scarcity of nuclear fuel resources.

The history of thorium-based fuel utilization can be broadly categorized into three distinct phases [2,3]:

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Figure 1. The nuclear reaction chain of the thorium-uranium fuel cycle.

- (1) Phase One (1960s-1970s): Driven by the rapid expansion of nuclear energy industry and consequent increased demand for nuclear fuel, extensive research into thorium utilization was conducted in Europe and North America. During this period, countries including the United States, Japan, the United Kingdom, and Canada employed thorium fuel in several experimental and power reactors.
- (2) Phase Two (1980s-1990s): Research and development on thorium fuel utilization was largely discontinued in many nations. This shift was attributed to the discovery of new uranium deposits, a subsequent decline in uranium prices, and the negative impact on nuclear energy development stemming from the 1986 Chernobyl nuclear accident.
- (3) Phase Three (after the 1990s): International interest in thorium fuel research was renewed, primarily motivated by its potential for the incineration of weapons-grade plutonium and its inherent proliferation resistance characteristics.

Theoretically, thorium can achieve breeding in helium-cooled High Temperature Gas-cooled Reactors (HTGRs), D₂O-cooled Heavy Water Reactors (HWRs), and Molten Salt Reactors (MSRs) [4]. HTGRs are well-suited for the utilization of thorium-based fuels. A key factor contributing to this suitability is the unique fuel design of HTGRs, which employs TRISO coated particles. This design enables significantly higher fuel burnup depths compared to conventional pressurized water reactors (PWRs), providing a distinct advantage for promoting the conversion of Th-232 to U-233. Additionally, the pebble-bed HTGR configuration utilizes spherical fuel elements, which permit continuous refueling and consequently provide enhanced flexibility in fuel management strategies. Historically, Germany's AVR [5,6] and THTR-300 [7,8] operated for periods utilizing mixed fuels composed of highly enriched uranium (HEU) and thorium. Teuchert [9] investigated the thorium-to-uranium conversion performance in HTGRs through a dual-reactor scheme. Gintner [10] assessed the feasibility of uranium fuel savings using thorium fuel based on the HTR-MODUL, which implemented a dual-reactor approach. Wols [11-13] designed a thorium-breeder pebble bed HTGR featuring a radial core zoning concept. Furthermore, HTGRs exhibit superior neutron economy, characterized by a larger thermal neutron flux fraction than PWRs. This enhanced thermal spectrum is more conducive to the breeding of U-233, enabling the realization of a thorium-based fuel cycle.

Utilizing thorium resources as an alternative to uranium for nuclear power generation represents a potential development pathway. Gen-IV (Generation IV) advanced nuclear energy systems, characterized by enhanced safety and improved economics, constitute the primary direction for future nuclear energy development. Integrating thorium-based fuels with these advanced systems can effectively promote the sustainable development of the nuclear energy industry.

The pebble bed HTGR has achieved substantial progress in recent years. In December 2023, High Temperature Reactor - Pebble bed Modules (HTR-PM) [14-17] designed by the Institute of Nuclear and New Energy Technology (INET), commenced commercial operation, signifying China's successful construction and operation of the world's first modular HTGR nuclear power plant. As one of primary reactor types in the Gen-IV advanced nuclear energy system, HTGRs exhibit inherent safety features. The pebble-bed HTGR employs spherical fuel elements resistant to high temperatures, utilizing helium as the coolant and graphite as both the moderator and core structural material. The spherical fuel elements of HTR-PM, measuring 6 cm in diameter, contain approximately 12,000 TRISO coated particles dispersed within the graphite matrix. The reactor design ensures that fuel temperature never exceeds the maximum limit of 1620 °C under any operational or accidental conditions [16], while TRISO coating layer design guarantees particle integrity at this temperature limit.

Currently, HTR-PM is operating stably. Conducting research on thorium-based fuel cycles for HTGRs based on this operational experience holds significant value. This paper designs thorium-based fuel loading patterns within the HTR-PM core and evaluates the near-breeding capability of the core under different loading schemes. Section 2 describes the core structure and fuel loading patterns. Section 3 presents the analysis and discussion of computational results. Section 4 provides the conclusions.

2. Core structure and fuel loading patterns

This section first introduces the core structure of HTR-PM, and then presents the fuel loading patterns.

2.1. Core structure

HTR-PM employs a modular design comprising two identical modules. Each module integrates a 250 MWt reactor connected to a steam generator, with both modules driving a single turbine for electricity generation. The main design parameters of HTR-PM are shown in Table I.

The region of active core, shaped as a regular 30-sided polygon, can be approximated as a cylinder with an equivalent diameter of 3 meters and an equivalent height of 11 meters. Spherical fuel elements are randomly distributed within the active core, achieving the volumetric packing fraction of approximately 0.61. Surrounding the active core is the graphite reflector. The reflector contains 24 control rod channels, 6 absorber ball channels, and 30 helium (as coolant) channels. An outer layer of boron-containing carbon brick serves as the neutron shield. During normal operation, power regulation is achieved through control rod manipulation.

Table I. Main design parameters of HTR-PM [18, 19].

Parameter	Unit	Value
Thermal power	MWt	2×250
Effective diameter/height of the reactor core	m	3/11
Helium temperature at reactor inlet/outlet	°C	250/750
Primary helium pressure	MPa	7
Primary helium flow rate	kg/s	96
Heavy metal loading per fuel pebble	g	7
Enrichment of fresh fuel pebble	%	8.5
Average discharged pebbles burnup	MWd/tHM	90,000
Average number for fuel pebble passing the core	-	15

2.2. Fuel loading patterns

Thorium is not a fissile nuclide, and Th-232 possesses a very low neutron reaction cross section. Consequently, thorium-based reactors require driver fuel to achieve criticality. Thorium-based HTGRs utilize ThO₂ as the fertile material and require UO₂ as the driver fissile material. The thorium-based HTGR design based on the HTR-PM presented in our study employs a configuration where ThO₂ and UO₂ fuels are combined within a single spherical fuel element, forming Mixed Oxide (MOX) fuel.

Spherical fuel element with a diameter of 6 cm, includes the graphite matrix with a diameter of 5 cm and the cladding with a thickness of 0.5 cm. TRISO coated particles are dispersed in the graphite matrix. The diameter of TRISO coated particle is 0.92 mm, and the center is fuel kernel with a diameter of about 0.55 mm, which are successively divided into porous pyrolytic carbon, inner pyrolytic carbon, silicon carbide and outer pyrolytic carbon from the inside to the outside. TRISO coated particles can block the release of almost all fission products, which is safer and has been widely used in HTGRs.

The thorium-uranium MOX fuel consists of two components: UO₂ and ThO₂. The fresh fuel contains three heavy metal nuclides—U-233, U-238, and Th-232—with U-233 being the only fissile nuclide. In our study, the proportion of U-233 in the total uranium element remains constant. The ratio of U-233 to heavy metal nuclides can be adjusted, and the enrichment of U-233 is defined as $m(\text{U-233})/m(\text{HM})$.

3. Key parameters affecting the conversion ratio

This section analyzes the key parameters affecting the conversion ratio.

Conversion Ratio (CR) is defined as the number of new fissile nuclei produced per fissile nucleus consumed in the reactor. The objective for the designed thorium-based fuel cycle in the HTGRs is to achieve breeding or near-breeding performance, corresponding to the CR greater than or close to 1.

The expression for the CR is:

$$CR = \eta - 1 - A - L + F \quad (1)$$

where η is the effective number of neutrons released per fission absorption, A represents the number of neutrons absorbed in non-fissile fuel materials per absorption in a fissile nucleus, L represents the number of neutrons leaking from the core per absorption in a fissile nucleus, F represents the fast fission contribution, defined as the number of neutrons produced through fast fission in fertile material per absorption in a fissile nucleus.

Achieving breeding ($CR > 1$) necessitates $\eta > 2$. U-233 exhibits the η greater than 2 in both thermal and fast neutron spectra. This superior neutronic performance compared to U-235 and Pu-239 makes U-233 potentially capable of achieving breeding even in thermal reactors. Consequently, converting Th-232 to U-233 via the thorium-based fuel cycle offers the potential for a breeding core. As seen in Equation (1), enhancing the CR primarily involves minimizing parasitic neutron absorption (reducing A) and neutron leakage (reducing L).

In the nuclear reaction chain converting Th-232 to U-233, Pa-233 is a crucial intermediate nuclide. Besides undergoing beta decay to form U-233, Pa-233 can also absorb a neutron to transform into Pa-234, with a significant absorption cross section. The change rate of Pa-233 atomic density over time is given by the following equation:

$$\frac{dN_{Pa233}}{dt} = \lambda_{Th233}N_{Th233} - (\sigma_{a,Pa233}\phi + \lambda_{Pa233})N_{Pa233} \quad (2)$$

where N is the atomic density (atoms/cm³), λ is the radioactive decay constant (s⁻¹), σ_a is the microscopic neutron absorption cross section (cm²), ϕ is the neutron flux density (neutrons/cm²-s).

To maximize the decay of Pa-233 into U-233, it is necessary to maximize the ratio $\lambda_{Pa233} / (\sigma_{a,Pa233} \times \phi)$. This implies that a low flux density is required to minimize the parasitic neutron absorption of Pa-233. Since flux density is proportional to power density, a low power density is more favorable for U-233 production. The power density of HTGRs – for example, approximately 3.2 MW/m³ in the HTR-PM – is significantly lower than that of typical PWRs, making HTGRs more conducive to achieving breeding.

This study focuses on the effects of three key parameters—discharge burnup, moderation ratio, and core size—on the conversion ratio. After a period of burnup, fission products continuously accumulate in the fuel. Burnup depth influences the conversion ratio, as fission products can absorb neutrons. The moderation ratio N_C/N_{HM} , which represents the proportion of moderation material (graphite) to heavy metal material in the core, affects the conversion ratio by influencing the effective number of fission neutrons and neutron absorption. Core size, particularly the radial dimension, has a significant impact on the conversion ratio due to its effect on neutron leakage.

4. Results and discussion

This study employs the VSOP [20] code for modeling and calculations. The VSOP code is a HTGR design program developed by the Jurich Research Center in Germany. Nuclear data libraries ENDF/B-V and JEF-1 are used in the VSOP code. The two-dimensional (r,z) geometry model is used for the physical calculation of the HTR-PM.

4.1. Discharge burnup

With moderation ratio keeps constant at 180, discharge burnup is adjusted to observe its effect on the conversion ratio. When discharge burnup is reduced, enrichment of fresh fuel can be decreased to maintain the criticality of reactor core. The calculation results are presented in Table II. It can be observed that as discharge burnup decreases, conversion ratio gradually increases, which is consistent with the qualitative analysis discussed earlier.

Table II. The effect of discharge burnup on the conversion ratio (moderation ratio = 180).

Parameter	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4
Discharged burnup (MWd/tHM)	40,000	30,000	20,000	10,000
Conversion ratio	0.795	0.802	0.815	0.837
Enrichment of U-233	5.35%	4.61%	3.90%	3.43%
Neutron absorption of fission products	3.96%	3.78%	3.39%	2.82%

A lower discharge burnup results in fewer fission products, thereby reducing parasitic neutron absorption and leading to a higher conversion ratio. The greater the reduction in neutron absorption of fission products, the more significant the increase in the conversion ratio. A correlation analysis between the conversion ratio and neutron absorption of fission products is conducted using mathematical

methods. The linear regression yields a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.999, indicating that parasitic neutron absorption of fission products plays a predominant role in the change of conversion ratio when discharge burnup changes.

Furthermore, even when discharge burnup is reduced to 10,000 MWd/tHM at a moderation ratio of 180, conversion ratio remains at only 0.839, indicating that breeding conditions have not yet been achieved.

4.2. Moderation ratio

This section investigates the variation of conversion ratio with changes in the moderation ratio while maintaining a constant discharge burnup. In this study, moderation ratio N_C/N_{HM} refers to the ratio of the number of graphite atoms to heavy metal nuclides. Due to graphite's lower moderation capability compared to water, HTGRs generally operate in the under-moderated state. When the moderation ratio is small, indicating less graphite and more heavy metal, the degree of under-moderated increases. Consequently, enrichment of U-233 in the fresh fuel must be raised to compensate for reactivity loss, as illustrated in Figure 2(a).

Figure 2. The enrichment of U-233 and conversion ratio under different discharge burnup and moderation ratio.

Table III. The effect of moderation ratio on the conversion ratio (discharge burnup 10,000 MWd/tHM).

Parameter	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
Moderation ratio	180	120	60
Conversion ratio	0.837	0.886	0.948
Enrichment of U-233	3.43%	4.58%	9.83%
Neutron leakage	10.54%	9.47%	9.16%
Neutron absorption of Pa-233	0.28%	0.19%	0.06%
Neutron absorption of Xe-135	1.64%	1.04%	0.12%

As shown in Figure 2(b), for the same discharge burnup, conversion ratio gradually increases as the moderation ratio decreases. A smaller moderation ratio, corresponding to a higher loading of heavy metal, results in a greater inventory of fissile material. This leads to an increase in the total absorption cross section, which reduces neutron leakage. Additionally, at the same power level, a higher density of

fissile material lowers the neutron flux density, thereby reducing parasitic absorption by Pa-233 and Xe-135. The (n,γ) cross section of Pa-233 drops drastically with higher neutron energy (i.e. with lower moderation), thereby reducing the parasitic absorption of Pa-233. These effects are more conducive to the breeding of U-233, as demonstrated in the results presented in Table III.

4.3. Core size

As observed in the previous two sections, conversion ratio reached 0.948—approaching breeding—by reducing the discharge burnup and increasing the moderation ratio. This section examines the influence of core size on the conversion ratio, primarily by expanding the radius of cylindrical core to reduce neutron leakage and further enhance the conversion ratio.

When modifying the core size, the power density of reactor core is maintained constant at 3.22 MW/m^3 . Thus, increasing the radius also results in a corresponding increase in total power. The discharge burnup and moderation ratio are kept unchanged at 10,000 MWd/tHM and 60, respectively.

An increase in the radius leads to degraded radial heat transfer performance, thereby raising the average fuel temperature. Owing to the negative temperature feedback effect inherent in HTGRs, temperature rise introduces negative reactivity. As a result, enrichment of U-233 in the fresh fuel must be increased to compensate for the reactivity loss, as summarized in Table IV.

When core radius reached 2.5 m, conversion ratio achieved a value of 1; further increasing the radius to 3 m resulted in a conversion ratio of 1.01, indicating the attainment of breeding. As observed in Table IV, both neutron leakage gradually decreased and conversion ratio progressively improved with increasing core radius. A correlation analysis between the conversion ratio and neutron leakage yielded a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.9997.

Table IV. The effect of core size on the conversion ratio (discharge burnup 10,000 MWd/tHM, moderation ratio 60).

Parameter	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4
Core radius (m)	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.0
Conversion ratio	0.948	0.981	1.000	1.010
Enrichment of U-233	9.83%	10.18%	10.36%	10.56%
Core thermal power (MWt)	250	445	695	1000
Average fuel temperature (°C)	584	591	599	623
Neutron leakage	9.16%	7.69%	6.87%	6.47%

5. Conclusion

Based on the HTR-PM design, this paper develops a physics scheme for implementing thorium-based fuel cycles in HTGRs. The aim is to achieve breeding or near-breeding in the core—that is, a conversion ratio greater than or close to 1—through the use of thorium-based fuel cycles.

The results demonstrate that discharge burnup, moderation ratio, and core size have significant impacts on the conversion ratio in thorium-based HTGRs. By reducing the discharge burnup, increasing the moderation ratio, and expanding the core radius, neutron leakage and parasitic neutron absorption can be reduced, thereby enhancing the conversion ratio. A breeding conversion ratio is expected to be achievable when the core radius exceeds 2.5 m based on the thorium fuel cycle.

Core physics design constitutes the first step in advancing thorium-based fuel cycle. Neutronic feasibility must first be confirmed before further investigation is justified. The practical implementation of thorium-based fuel cycle also requires addressing a range of engineering challenges, including fuel manufacturing, reprocessing, and related issues.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors gratefully appreciate the support from the LingChuang Research Project of China National Nuclear Corporation.

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